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TRT EBA Secondary School Channel Social Studies Courses: Attitude and Perceptions of Students

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the attitudes and perceptions of secondary school students, who live in Bingöl and take social studies course, towards this course broadcasted on TRT EBA (Education Information Network) secondary school channel in the second semester of the 2019-2020 academic year. A quantitative research approach was adopted and a cross-sectional survey design was used in the study. The population of the study is 150 students who are in the 5th, 6th and 7th grades of the secondary school located within the borders of Bingöl city center in the 2019-2020 academic year. The data collection tool is the "scale of attitudes and perceptions towards social studies course broadcasted on TRT EBA secondary school channel " developed by the researchers. Factor analysis, correlation analysis, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test were used on the scale. Cronbach's Alpha test was conducted for the reliability of the measurements. IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences 22.0 (SPSS, Chicago, IL) was used for data analysis. Independent Samples t-test and One-Way ANOVA were applied for differences of general attitudes and perceptions. It was concluded that the attitudes and perceptions of the students are on the border of positive-neutral; social studies courses were not presented in a way to attract the attention of students; and that some changes are needed regarding the studio environment and the presentation of the courses.

Keywords: Student Perceptions, Social Studies, TRT EBA Secondary School, Attitude and Perception Scale

1. Introduction

In the twenty-first century, rapid social, economic and technological developments experienced all over the world have made changes in education inevitable. Countries around the world have had to act on strengthening the technological infrastructure, especially in education. Day by day, the traditional understanding of school has begun to be replaced by the understanding of school without physical boundaries. Societies have been urged to completely changing their understanding of limiting traditional school education between walls, especially with the Covid-19 pandemic (Akkaş Baysal et al., 2020).

World societies have come across or have been brought against the virus pandemic, which is reported to originate in Wuhan, China and allegedly produced as part of the Human 2.0 project. It also contains a global transformation, technological monopoly and brings many arguments related to it. The turning of this pandemic into a rapid threat has brought different measures and practices to the agenda. The field of education has also been affected by these measures and practices. In Turkey, some steps taken by the Ministry of Education (MEB) long before the pandemic made a significant contribution to the management of this process. In 2010, with the Movement of Enhancing Opportunities and Improving Technology (FATİH), the project of financing project implementation support was initiated with the delivery of broadband internet to all classes, the provision of e-content of the courses, the adaptation of teachers to information communication technologies and the establishment of web platforms for content development (MEB, 1). MEB offered free online opportunities to education stakeholders with the Education Information Network (EBA), which was designed as a social platform in 2012. Thus, it continues to integrate technology into education through information technologies and share reliable and reviewed e-contents suitable for class levels (MEB, 2). These include lecture, news, video, visual, audio, book, magazine, document, competition, e-course, distance education and lifelong learning and television sections. The EBA application is also offered as already installed on tablet computers distributed within the scope of the FATİH Project. Thus, new applications can be downloaded, and existing ones can be updated (Coşkunserçe et al., 2019). Through EBA, students can access lecture notes, projects and assignments, share their works with their teachers and classmates, and go over the topics they learn through supplementary materials. In 2020, EBA started to broadcast live as soon as the epidemic erupted (Çiftçi et al., 2020). Thanks to this infrastructure, MEB was able to quickly take measures for distance and online education types that are needed more intensively due to the pandemic. The developments in the pandemic process and the pressures of global mechanisms in the direction of digitalization have shown that distance education is no longer seen as supplementary or a substitute for face-to-face education, as it has been until today, and that there is no alternative to distance education (Türker et al., 2020). However, the digital gap between different groups' access to these technological tools due to socio-economic differences in distance education practices is a significant problem. In particular, groups such as Romani people, children of seasonal agricultural worker families, and refugee children also experience the digital gap significantly (Sezgin et al.2020). In order to overcome the digital gap problem, distance education via television, which is more common than the internet, has enabled education and instruction to reach every home easily. Thus, the principle of equality and fairness in education could be ensured (Aydın, 2020). After the Covid-19 outbreak was announced in other countries, television and radio broadcasts came to the fore with internet applications. Broadcasting from television and radio has gained importance as an alternative to people who do not have internet or computer access or to the internet applications that are difficult to access because of many people trying to access them simultaneously (Eken et al., 2020). The Ministry of Education opted for the most effective way and established three new television channels quickly. TRT EBA Primary School, TRT EBA Secondary School and TRT EBA High School started distance education on March 23, 2020. Students could watch their lectures in alternative hours determined according to the program of their classes. Thus, when over 1.5 billion students worldwide were deprived of face-to-face education in 184 countries, Turkey became the second country that started a nationwide distance education (MEB, 3). TRT EBA channels broadcasted 2516 hours until June 19, 2020, which is the beginning of the summer holiday. In order to strengthen this one-way communication, the pilot implementation of the live classroom application of the online EBA platform, which enables multi-directional lessons, started on March 30, 2020. During the pandemic period, the EBA platform was actively used by 7.383.213 students and 1.300.516 teachers (MEB, 4).

A one-hour course program consisting of two lessons per day was designed for primary and secondary schools on TRT EBA channels. The courses are Turkish, Mathematics, Social Studies, English, Science, Social Studies, Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge and Arabic, respectively. For high schools, a one-hour and thirty-minute course program consisting of three lessons a day was designed. Courses are Turkish Language and Literature, Mathematics, Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge, History, Chemistry, Mathematics, Biology, Physics, Geography, Philosophy, English, History of Revolution and Kemalism. An "activity zone" of one hour or one hour and thirty minutes was also added to these lessons (Eren, 2020). Some studies show that students are satisfied with EBA in functional and communication aspects (Sentürk et al., 2020). It was reported that all students had easy access to distance education courses and participated willingly (Gören et al., 2020). Despite all these possibilities, it was revealed that teachers think that distance education cannot be a substitute for learning

by doing and living (Ünal et al., 2020). In Aydın's (2020) research, it was stated that an overwhelming majority of the secondary school students enjoyed watching the content related to the Turkish lesson and found the programs informative, but stated that the duration of the lessons and the number of activities should be increased. In her research with primary school parents, İnci Kuzu (2020) concluded that the students watched the lessons on EBA TV enthusiastically, and a great majority of them were connected right on time when the lessons started and did not have concentration problems until the end of the lesson, and liked the lessons. Şentürk et al. (2020) concluded that in distance education via EBA, female students had a more positive perspective in the communication dimension than male students, there was no significant difference between secondary school classes in terms of functionality and motivation, and in the communication dimension, the fifth and sixth graders had more positive perceptions than the eighth graders. Despite the widespread use of the Internet, television remains a popular medium to reach people. However, in a study conducted in nine different provinces, it was determined that secondary school students did not consider EBA TV broadcasts alone sufficient, the lessons were not engaging, but they thought distance education was conducted in a healthy way (Kaynar et al., 2020). In another study, it was found that perceptions about EBA TV lessons and broadcast flow were generally positive, but teachers' teaching only on the board and not using any other method decreased student motivation, students felt negative about teachers' reading the slides on the board, the time was sufficient, the exercises were enough, and as the grade level increased, the content and the presentation of the subjects taught grew more insufficient (Erümit, 2020). The students stated that they only watched EBA TV lessons, could not participate actively, teachers could not get answers to their questions, and feedback could not be provided (Başaran et al., 2020). A study conducted regarding English lessons concluded that EBA TV has many points to be appreciated; however, further improvements are needed in terms of material, efficiency, and some technical issues (Özkanal et al., 2020). In the study conducted on 7th-grade Turkish lessons, it was concluded that subjects containing only information were presented in TRT EBA channels, the lessons were carried out with concept definitions and explanations and prepared in a format that guided students to memorization, but students received support so that they do not become feel alienated from the practices they are used to in schools (Akin, 2020). It was determined that the education provided on the EBA TV throughout the country offers equal opportunity, the limitation of using different materials negatively affects learning; on the other hand, the flexibility in the lessons, the ability to review and reinforce are seen as an advantage (Başaran et al., 2020).

These results show that distance education should be developed in its various aspects. MEB, which is constantly striving to further its research and development activities, organized the "Intelligent Technologies and Software Development Professional Development Program" as part of the preparation for the Internet of Things applications, one of the main concepts of the New World order. The program was organized for the teachers. The program aimed to provide teachers with smart technology and software development training to make sure that students are raised as individuals who use technology effectively, who have strong competencies and who have acquired the skills that the business world needs. After 8-week training provided to 1032 teachers, the goal is to reach a total of 1 million current teachers, including 19 thousand information technology teachers (MEB, 5).

In this study, in order to contribute to the development of TRT EBA TV programs in general and social studies presentations and the relevant literature in particular, the attitudes and perceptions of secondary school students living in Bingöl towards the social studies lessons offered on the TRT EBA Secondary School channel were determined.

1.2. The Aim of the Study

The aim of this study was to determine the attitudes and perceptions of secondary school students living in Bingöl and taking social studies course towards social studies courses offered on TRT EBA secondary school channel in the second semester of the 2019-2020 academic year.

1.3. Main and Sub-Questions of the Study

The main research question of this study is expressed with the question of “What are the attitudes of secondary school students living in Bingöl and taking social studies course towards social studies courses offered on TRT EBA Secondary School channel?”. Sub-questions determined depending on this main question are as follows:

1. What are the perceptions of secondary school students about the studio environment where social studies courses are offered on the TRT EBA Secondary School channel?
2. What are their perceptions on the comprehensibility of the social studies course on the TRT EBA Secondary School channel?
3. What are their attitudes towards the presentation of social studies courses on the TRT EBA Secondary School channel?
4. How is the comparison of their attitudes towards social studies courses on the TRT EBA Secondary School channel with their attitudes towards social studies courses offered at school?
5. What are their general attitude and perceptions towards social studies lessons on the TRT EBA Secondary School channel?
6. Is there a significant difference by gender between attitudes or perceptions towards social studies courses on the TRT EBA Secondary School channel?
7. Is there a significant difference between their attitudes or perceptions towards social studies courses on the TRT EBA Secondary School channel according to grade levels?

2. Method

In this section, the research design, population and sample, data collection and analysis methods of the research are included.

2.1. Research Pattern

This study was designed according to a quantitative research approach, and a cross-sectional survey design was employed. The rationale for choosing this pattern is to illustrate the determined population's attitudes and perceptions towards the social studies course offered in distance education via television by means of a sample group and to collect information on this subject. Statistical analysis was carried out with the data obtained in accordance with this design, the tendency of the data was defined, and the research questions were answered. Accordingly, current attitudes, beliefs, perceptions or practices can be examined, and across-group comparisons can be made with the cross-sectional survey design (Creswell, 2019). This study also aimed to compare 5th, 6th and 7th-grade student attitudes. The attitudes, beliefs and perceptions here include the way individuals think about a subject (Creswell, 2019).

2.2. Population and Sample

The population of the study is the 5th, 6th and 7th-grade students at secondary schools located within the borders of Bingöl province centre in the 2019-2020 academic year. These levels were chosen because social studies courses are included in their curriculum. The study sample is a total of 150 students, 72 girls and 78 boys, who were selected in accordance with the probability-based stratified sampling technique in the universe. Grade levels were accepted as a variable, and grade-based stratification was made. Care was taken to have an equal number of students by gender in each stratum. By taking into account a certain variable, the representation of the variable's characteristics in the sample at the same rate is called stratified sampling (Altunışık et al., 2005). Simple random sampling was used in the selection of members within the stratum. While determining the number of samples, 50 students from each grade level were contacted since sample sizes greater than 30 and smaller than 500 are sufficient for many studies. In the event that the samples are divided into subgroups, the sample size of each category should be at least 30 people. In this study, it is accepted that each class constitutes a subgroup. However, it is also recommended to reach a sample size of at least ten times the number of variables in the data collection form (Altunışık et al., 2005). Since this study finally consists of 14 items, the completion of the study with 150 students shows the adequacy of the sample size. The ability to track the attendance online

facilitated taking the necessary steps in the sampling. The distribution of the participants according to their grade levels and genders is presented in Table 1:

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distributions of students according to gender and grade levels

Gender	Grade Level						Total	
	5th Grade		6th Grade		7th Grade		f	%
	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Male	32	64	24	48	22	44	78	52
Female	18	36	26	52	28	56	72	48

According to Table 1, 78 (52%) of the participating students are female, and 72 (48%) are male. There are 50 students from all grade levels. 32 (64%) of the 5th-grade students are female, 18 (36%) of them are male, 24 (48%) of the 6th-grade students are female (%), 26 (52%) are male, and 22 (44%) of the 7th-grade students are female, and 28 (56%) are male.

2.3. Data Collection Method of the Study

In the study, "the scale of attitudes and perceptions towards TRT EBA secondary school channel" developed by the researchers was used. Prior to the study, the content of the research and the scale to be used were presented to the Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Board of Bingöl University, and it was verified that the application was in accordance with the research ethics with the letter dated 13/07/2020 and numbered E.11829. The scale consists of Likert-type items, and each item consists of 5 categories. The items were structured to answer the research questions and to use the mean values of these questions in the analysis phase. In the first stage, 23 items were determined. The items were composed of clear, short, single and balanced positive-negative statements. Negative implications and guiding expressions were avoided. The items were submitted to two social studies teachers' perceptions, one of whom with five years and the other with eight years of professional experience, one literature teacher with 16 years of experience and two experts with a Ph.D. degree in social studies. A total of 6 items, which received a negative opinion from any of them, were cancelled, and only 17 items with complete consensus were included in the scale. In the preliminary test of the draft scale, the items' comprehensibility and items completion time were measured on 18 students. Accordingly, it was decided to exclude three more items from the scale, and some minor changes were performed. As in its final form, the scale encompasses a cover letter stating the importance of participation, the aim of the study, and a strict guarantee of participant confidentiality. It also encompasses socio-demographic questions consisting of school, class and gender information and 14 items prepared according to the 5-point Likert scale, which aim to determine the attitudes and perceptions of the participants regarding presentations of teachers, the environment where the presentations are executed, the comprehensibility of the lessons, the comparison between the lesson from the television and the lesson in the school. Scale options are listed as I strongly agree (1), I agree (2), I am indecisive (3), I do not agree (4), and I strongly disagree (5).

The scale, which took its final form, was structured on a website for a charge, and the web connection of the scale was formed in order not to pose any health risks due to the Covid 19 pandemic and to make it possible to collect data due to the summer break of schools. Teachers and parents were contacted to deliver the web link to students, and their support was received, provided that they comply with the voluntary principle. The link was made available to 5th, 6th, and 7th-grade students, respectively. For one level, taking into account the gender as much as possible, the action was not taken for another level before the sample had reached a sufficient number. The scales filled in online were followed daily, those that were found to be not filled insincerely were cancelled, and this continued until it reached 150 students. Factor analysis was performed to test the construct validity of the scale. Factor analysis is a set of multivariate methods aiming to determine the fewer number of new variables that are independent, conceptually meaningful, with as little information loss as possible from many interrelated variables. The purpose of the analysis is to reduce dimensions and classify variables by investigating the structure in the relationships between variables (Alpar, 2017). Factor structure was measured by correlation analysis. The suitability of the data for factor analysis was evaluated using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and

Bartlett's Test. KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy is a method used to measure the studied sample's suitability for factor analysis. KMO ranges between 0-1. For good factor analysis, the KMO measure is expected to be more than 0.80. However, a KMO value above 0.60 is seen as sufficient most of the time, while being below 0.50 is unacceptable for factor analysis (Alpar, 2016). As a result of the analysis, the KMO value was calculated as 0.748. The minimum KMO value considered satisfactory by the researchers is 0.7 (as cited in Malhotra, 1996; Altunışık et al., 2005). This result, for instance, indicates that the sample size of the scale is satisfactory. Bartlett's test of sphericity was conducted to measure whether the data were suitable for factor analysis. The result of the test was significant ($X^2 = 636.735$; $p < 0.01$). This situation showed that the data were suitable for factor analysis. In the factor analysis of the scale, four factors that explained 75.2% of the total variance with an eigenvalue greater than one emerged. Varimax was used as a data return method. The return process was applied in 15 iterations. Thus, highly related items were collected under the same factor. It was observed that there was no need to remove any items to increase the scale's reliability. The 14-item scale consists of 4 factors in this way. The eigenvalue, variance percentages and total variance percentages of the factors are presented in Table 2:

Table 2: The eigen values of the scale factors and the amount of variance they explained

Factors	Eigenvalue	Percentage of Variance	Total Variance Percentage
1	3.078	27.481	27.481
2	2.541	22.384	49.865
3	1.672	14.453	64.318
4	1.341	10.883	75.201

According to Table 2, the amount of the total variance explained by the four factors is 75.201%. The variance must be above at least 66% (Alpar, 2017). The eigenvalue of the first factor is 3.078, and it explains 27.481% of the total variance, the eigenvalue of the second factor is 2.541, and it explains 22.384% of the total variance, the eigenvalue of the third factor is 1.672, and it explains 14.453% of the total variance, the eigenvalue of the fourth factor is 1.341, and it explains 10.883% of the total variance. Factors were named as perceptions regarding the studio environment, perceptions regarding understanding the lessons, attitudes towards presentation, and attitudes towards the course's choice on TV and school.

In order to strengthen the construct validity, the relations of the subscales with the whole scale and with each other were tested with Pearson correlation coefficients. Pearson correlation coefficients for this scale range between 0.372 and 0.915. Coefficients are significant at the 0.01 level ($p < 0.01$). Accordingly, it can be said that there is a significant relationship between the whole scale and its sub-dimensions and significant relationships between the sub-dimensions and the distinctiveness of the items is overall high.

The Cronbach Alpha test, known as internal consistency calculation, was used to calculate the reliability of the measurements obtained from the 14 items in the measurement tool. Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is used to predict the reliability of a psychometric test. If the coefficient is found to be 0.7 and above, the reliability of the scale is accepted as good (Kılıç, 2016). Since the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of this test was found to be 0.73, it is reliable. The minimum score to be obtained from this scale is 14, and the highest score is 70. Since the scale is a 5-point Likert type, the lowest average to be obtained from the scale is 1, and the highest average is 5.

2.4. Data Analysis

A 5-point Likert scale was used in the study. This scale aims to determine the average attitudes of the participants on the specified topics from the combined values of all items. (Turan et al., 2015). The data obtained from the scale were entered into the IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences 22.0 (SPSS, Chicago, IL) package program. While doing this, necessary transformations were made for negative questions.

In order to determine if the general attitudes and perceptions of the students towards social studies lessons offered on television differ according to gender or not, Independent Samples t-test, and in order to determine if there is a difference according to grade levels, one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) was carried out. The scoring key of the Likert scale is presented in Table 3:

Table 3: Scoring key

Attitude	Values	Result
I strongly disagree	14-21	Very Negative
I disagree	22-35	Negative
I'm indecisive	36-49	Neutral (Indecisive)
I agree	50-63	Positive
I strongly agree	64-70	Very positive

According to Table 3, in case that the average of a student's markings on the Likert scale is between 14-21, the attitude and perceptions of the students regarding the social studies course broadcasted on the TRT EBA secondary school channel will be interpreted as very negative, if between 22-3, as negative, if between 36-49, as neutral (indecisive), if between 50-63, as positive, and if between 64-70, as very positive. In order to make a general evaluation, the average value of each student's scores was divided into 70, which is the highest score. Thus, it became possible to comment on the general approach.

3. Findings

In this section, the findings of the study related to the sub-questions are discussed.

3.1. Findings Related to Question 1 of the Study: Perceptions Regarding the Studio Environment

There is a teacher and a smart board just behind the teacher on the screen where social studies lessons are presented. Most of the time, the teacher covers a part of the board due to where they stand. The item "The studio where social studies lessons are broadcasted should remain as it is" was submitted to the students, and they were asked to express their perceptions about this studio environment. Perceptions are presented in Table 4:

Table 4: Students' perceptions regarding the studio environment

Item No	I strongly agree		I agree		I'm indecisive		I strongly disagree		I disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
6	26	17.3	39	26.0	35	23.3	39	26.0	11	7.3

According to Table 4, 43.3% of the students' perceptions regarding keeping the studio environment in which the lessons are broadcasted in the same form are very positive or positive, 23.3% of them are neutral, and 33.3% are negative or very negative.

Researchers thought that the presence of animated characters and teaching the lessons by professional vocalization as an alternative to teacher presentations on the screen on which social studies lessons were broadcast could be an alternative. In this way, it will be possible for the lessons to be more enriched and active with the animated characters, and they will be more fun. Therefore, the item "Animated characters should present lectures instead of teachers who offer social studies lessons." was presented to the students, and they were asked to express their perceptions on this issue. Perceptions are presented according to Table 5:

Table 5: Students' perceptions on the presentation of the lessons by the animated characters instead of teachers

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
4	26	17.3	42	28.0	29	19.3	24	16.0	29	19.3

According to Table 5, 45.3% of students' perceptions regarding the presentation of the lessons by the animated characters instead of teachers are very positive or positive, 19.3% are neutral, and 35.3% are negative or very negative.

It was thought that organizing the current studio environment like a real classroom environment could motivate students. For this reason, the item "The studio where social studies lessons are presented should be designed like a real classroom environment" was presented to the students, and they were asked to express their perceptions. Perceptions are presented in Table 6:

Table 6: Students' perceptions regarding designing the studio like a real classroom environment

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
5	51	34.0	53	35.0	29	19.3	11	7.3	6	4.0

According to Table 6, 69% of the students' perceptions about designing the studio like a classroom environment are very positive or positive, 19.3% neutral and 11.3% negative or very negative.

It was thought that designing the studio like a classroom environment and having animated characters seated in the desks while giving lectures on TV would be more fun for the students. For this reason, the item "The studio should be designed like a classroom, and animated characters should sit in the rows in the social studies course." was presented to the students, and they were asked to express their perceptions. Perceptions are presented in Table 7:

Table 7: Students' perceptions regarding having animated characters in the classroom environment

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
7	27	18.0	63	42.0	23	15.3	23	15.3	14	9.3

According to Table 7, 60% of the students' perceptions regarding having animated characters in the studio, which will be designed like a classroom environment, are very positive or positive, 15.3% are neutral, and 24.6% are negative or very negative.

3.2. Findings Regarding the Second Question of the Study: Understanding the Lessons

It is important to determine how well the teachers who present the lessons are understood in terms of both the method and the material they use. For this reason, the item "I understand social studies lessons." was presented to the students, and they were asked to express their perceptions on how well they understand the lessons. Their perceptions are presented in Table 8:

Table 8: Students' Perceptions Regarding Understanding Teachers

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
10	44	29.3	56	37.3	14	9.3	34	22.7	2	1.3

According to Table 8, 66.6% of students' perceptions about understanding teachers are very positive or positive, 9.3% are neutral and 24% are negative or very negative.

When social studies lessons on television begin, teachers give topic information about the subject they will present. However, if the content is not sufficiently correlated during the presentation, this leads to the loss of awareness regarding the subject being taught. For this reason, regarding whether the students are aware of the subject taught, the item "I am aware of the subjects that the social studies course teachers teach." was presented to the students, and they were asked to express their perceptions. Perceptions are presented in Table 9:

Table 9: Students' perceptions on subject matter awareness

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
11	35	23.3	81	54.0	15	10.0	18	12.0	1	0.7

According to Table 9, 77.3% of students' perceptions about the awareness of the subject matter are very positive or positive, 10% are neutral and 12.7% are negative or very negative.

The concepts mentioned in the lecture presentations are explained. However, it is important to determine the adequacy of the explanations for the students. For this reason, the item "I understand the concepts of social studies lesson." was submitted, and they were asked to express their perceptions. Perceptions are presented in Table 10:

Table 10: Students' perceptions regarding understanding the concepts

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
12	33	22.0	84	56.0	16	10.7	9	6.0	8	5.3

According to According to Table 10, 78% of students' perceptions about understanding concepts are very positive or positive, 10.7% are neutral and 11.3% are negative or very negative.

Since there is a relationship between the students' level of understanding the lesson and the length of the lesson, the item "The length of the social studies lessons should be increased." was submitted to the students, and they were asked to express their perceptions. Perceptions are presented in Table 11:

Table 11. Students' perceptions on increasing the lesson length

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
13	19	12.7	47	1.3	31	20.7	41	27.3	12	8.0

According to Table 11, 14% of the students' perceptions regarding increasing the length of the lesson are very positive or positive, 20.7% are neutral, and 35.3% are negative or very negative.

Since the boredom of the students would negatively affect how well students understand of the lessons, the item, "I get bored while watching social studies lessons" was submitted to the students, and they were asked to indicate their attitudes towards the lesson. The attitudes are presented in Table 12:

Table 12: Students' attitudes towards getting bored while watching the lessons

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
14	23	15.3	43	28.7	33	22.0	45	30.0	6	4.0

According to Table 12, 44% of the students' perceptions about their boredom in social studies lessons offered on television are very positive or positive, 22% are neutral and 34% are negative or very negative.

3.3. Findings Regarding the 3rd Question of the Study: Perceptions Regarding the Presentation of the Lessons

Teachers usually give monologue-style lectures in the lessons. It was thought that teachers could address questions to students to go beyond this lecturing pattern and motivate students in front of the screen and create a perception of reality. This practice is carried out at the primary school level. In order to understand whether a secondary school student wants such a style or not, the item "Questions aimed at students should be asked in social studies lesson" was submitted to the students, and they were asked to express their perceptions. Perceptions are presented in Table 13:

Table 13: Students perceptions regarding teachers' asking questions to them

Item	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	50	33.3	67	44.7	24	16.0	8	5.3	1	0.7

According to Table 13, 78% of the students' perceptions about that teachers ask questions as if students are present in the classroom are very positive or positive, 16% are neutral, and 6% are negative or very negative.

In the lecture presentations, lectures are sometimes taught using animated videos. In order to determine the students' attitudes towards this kind of practice, the item "I like the animated lectures in the social studies course" was submitted to the students, and they were asked to indicate their attitude. The attitudes are presented in Table 14:

Table 14: Students' attitudes towards the use of animated videos

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
2	77	51.3	64	42.7	6	4.0	0	0	3	2.0

While making presentations, teachers usually read from the slides on the smartboard or papers in their hands. In order to understand the students' attitudes towards this kind of lecturing, the item "I like that social studies teachers read the subject on the board or the paper in their hands" was submitted to the students, and they were asked to express their attitude. The attitudes are presented in Table 15:

Table 15: The attitudes of students towards teachers' lecturing by reading from paper

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
3	33	22.0	39	26.0	23	15.3	30	20.0	25	16.7

According to Table 15, 48% of students' attitudes towards teachers' lecturing by reading from paper are very positive or positive, 15.3% are neutral, and 36.7% are negative and very negative.

3.4. Findings Regarding the 4th Question of the Study: The Preference of Social Studies Lessons in School and Social Studies Lessons on TV

It was thought that determining whether students prefer social studies lessons at school or social studies lessons on television would be important in terms of determining the efficiency of the lessons. For this reason, the item "I prefer social studies lessons at school to social studies lessons broadcasted on TRT EBA secondary school channel" was submitted to the students, and they were asked to indicate their attitude. The attitudes are presented in Table 16:

Table 16: Students' attitudes towards preferring social studies courses at school

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
8	85	56.7	34	22.7	14	9.3	13	8.7	4	2.7

According to Table 16, 79.4% of the perceptions of students about their attitudes towards preferring social studies courses at school are very positive or positive, 9.3% are neutral, and 11.4% are negative.

In order to understand whether the students prefer the social studies lessons on TV or the social studies lessons at the school, the item, "I prefer the social studies lessons on the TRT EBA Secondary School channel to the social studies lessons in the school" was submitted, and they were asked to indicate their attitude on this issue. At the same time, the opposite of the item above was asked, and their attitudes were double confirmed. The item also served to show whether the scale was understood and completed. The attitudes are presented in Table 17:

Table 17: Students' attitudes towards preferring social studies courses on television

Item No	I Strongly Agree		I Agree		I'm Indecisive		I Strongly Disagree		I Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
9	11	7.3	15	10.0	15	10.0	42	28.0	67	44.7

According to Table 17, 17.3% of the students' attitudes towards preferring social studies courses offered on television are very positive and positive, 10% are neutral, and 72.7% are negative and very negative.

3.5. Findings Regarding The 5th Question of The Study: Students' General Attitudes and Perceptions Towards Social Studies Lessons on TRT EBA Secondary School

It was determined that the general attitude of the 150 students participating in the study was neutral with 49.28 ± 5.58 points, which is close to positive. Statistics related to this are presented in Table 18:

Table 18: General attitude and perception statistics towards social studies lessons broadcasted on TRT EBA Secondary School channel

N	Minimum Score	Maximum Score	Mean	Standard Deviation	Median	Variance	%95 Confidence Interval
150	33.00	66.00	49.28	5.58	49.00	31.09	48.38-50.18

According to Table 18, among the students participating in the study, the lowest attitude score is 33, and the highest attitude score is 66. The mean attitude score is 49.28. This score indicates the state of indecisiveness, close to positive. The standard deviation of 5.58 indicates the scattering of the scores around the mean. This difference between deviation reveals that students' attitudes and perceptions show a very different distribution from each other. The fact that the 95% confidence interval is in a very narrow band between 48.38-50.18 shows that the data shows a normal distribution, and there is an accumulation around the mean. The histogram graph of these data is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Histogram Graph of General Attitude and Perception Score towards Social Studies Lessons on TRT EBA Secondary School Channel

In Figure 1, the graph of the scores obtained from the scale according to the number of people is shown.

3.6. Findings Concerning the 6th Question of the Study: Attitude Differentiation According to Genders

According to the results of the independent sample t-test, it was found that there was no statistically significant difference in the general attitudes of the students towards social studies lessons presented on television according to gender ($p > 0.05$; $t = 0.209$).

3.7. Findings Regarding the 7th Question of the Study: Attitude Differentiation According to Grade Levels

According to the one-way analysis of variance, it was found that there was no statistically significant difference between students' general attitudes towards social studies lessons broadcasted on television, according to their grade level ($p > 0.05$; $F = 1.747$).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In the present study, it was aimed to analyse secondary school students' attitudes and behaviours about social studies lessons broadcasted on the TRT EBA Secondary School channel. In this context, it was determined that student attitudes and perceptions are on the border of indecision, very close to positive. On the one hand, the indecisiveness or neutrality can be ascribed to the fact that students are freed from spending a whole day under control and discipline with the closure of schools and reach a free environment they desire, but on the other hand, that they struggle in an undesirable situation due to losing their social environment. However, it is also a clear result that social studies courses were not presented in a way that attracted students. It cannot be ignored that there are some important reasons for this negative situation. The Ministry of National Education (MEB) was partially caught unprepared for the online classes due to the unexpected closure of the schools. Also, the shortcomings happened in the rush lesson shots, and the pressure was mounted on the institution because these lessons had to be presented on the screens in less than a month. However, in the studies, it was stated that there were positive attitudes and perceptions regarding the lecture presentations made on television after the epidemic. For example, in the study by Aydın (2020), it was stated that secondary school students enjoyed watching Turkish lessons. İnci Kuzu (2020) concluded in a study conducted with primary school students' parents that the students enjoyed watching the lectures on TV and did not experience concentration problems. The difference between this study and the studies mentioned above has shown that social studies lesson presentations are not performed with the correct methods. This statement is supported by the findings that the majority of secondary school students do not want the length of the lessons to be increased, state that they are bored with the lessons, and as stated in Erümit (2020), they generally find the lesson length sufficient. However, in Aydın's (2020) study, it was determined that students wanted the length of the lessons to be increased. This result shows that

students have a positive attitude towards the presentation of the Turkish lesson, and consequently, they want the lesson to last longer.

Another study that is similar to the result of this one is the study by Kaynar et al. (2020). In their research conducted in nine different provinces, they concluded that secondary school students generally did not find EBA TV broadcasts interesting. The reasons for this lack of interest are revealed in Erümit's (2020) study. The reasons for boredom are that teachers only give lectures on the board, do not use any other methods, and read from the slides on the board. In the study by Başaran et al. (2020), it was determined that students did not like one-way communication. This study revealed what should be done so that students develop a more positive attitude towards the lessons. Although the majority of the students show a positive attitude towards the studio environment consisting of a teacher and a smart board behind it, students suggested that they want animated characters to make presentations instead of teachers, want their teachers to ask questions to them as if they are in the classroom, want the screen to be decorated like a real classroom setting and want the animated characters to sit in the desks to reduce this boredom and to make lessons more attractive and fun. Özkanalet al. (2020) concluded that EBA TV has many points to be appreciated, but further improvements are needed in terms of material, activity and some technical issues. Akın (2020) also found that subjects containing only information are presented on TRT EBA TV, the lessons are carried out with concept definitions and explanations, and prepared in a format that directs students to memorization. These results also show that it is necessary to take into account the student suggestions mentioned above.

In the study, it was determined that there is no difference between the secondary school grade levels in terms of attitudes and perceptions towards social studies lessons presented on television. This situation is similar to the results of the studies by Şentürk, Duran & Yılmaz (2020). In their study, they reported that there was no significant difference between secondary school grades in terms of functionality and motivation for distance education.

It is also among the important results of the study that most of the students understand the teachers who give presentations, that the teachers follow the subject they teach consciously, but most of the students prefer the social studies lessons at school to the social studies lessons on the television. Despite all these possibilities, it was determined that teachers also think that distance education cannot be an alternative to learning by doing and living (Ünal & Bulunuz, 2020).

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